

22NRM03 “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport”

Report A2.2.1

SELECTION OF HYDROGEN SAMPLING STRATEGIES FOR HD-HRS

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Submission date of the deliverable/report: 1st February 2024

Revision date of the deliverable/report: -

Summary

This report was written as part of activity A2.1.1 from the Partnership on Metrology project “Metrology to support standardisation of hydrogen fuel sampling for heavy duty hydrogen transport” (MetHyTrucks). The three-year European project started 1st June 2023.

This report describes three potential sampling strategies identified for the application of heavy-duty sampling of particulate matter from HRS. The report discusses the adaptations needed for two commercial sampling devices that will be used in other activities in the project. Additionally, a filter holder designed for HD applications will be discussed with respect to the discussions around designing a system around it.

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1 Introduction

Heavy duty applications (HD) currently hold a lot of focus in Europe. With the updated AFIR directive, it is clear that hydrogen fuelling infrastructure targets long-haul heavy-duty vehicles and pre-normative and normative work needs to be underpinned in order to adapt refuelling protocols to allow for higher mass flows for efficient fuelling of these vehicles.

Hydrogen-powered vehicles require pure hydrogen as some contaminants can reduce the performance of the fuel cell even at very low levels. Previous projects have paved the way for the development of the European quality infrastructure for hydrogen conformity assessment. Traditionally, focus has been on sampling and analysis of gaseous impurities in hydrogen fuel rather than on particulate matter which also needs to be assessed according to EN 17124:2022 [1] and ISO 14687:2019 [2] hydrogen fuel quality specification standards. Projects like FCH-JU funded HyCoRA and Hydraite mostly report on gaseous impurities found in hydrogen dispensed at HRS. This is also the case for the EURAMET funded project, 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2 [3] even though some activities were dedicated to the sampling of particulate matter. However, it is expected that increased mass flow rates will affect particulate sampling, in particular, higher flow may have a direct impact on the particulate penetration through the filter membrane and on the integrity of the filter. Therefore, adaptation of the sampling systems and methods to the conditions prevailing in HD applications will be required.

For MetHyTrucks [4], the aim of Task 2.2 is to adapt existing, or design new particulate sampling devices for HD applications before they can be tested and validated at HD fuelling stations.

This report will report the survey performed and contacts taken to identify at least two potential candidates for HD sampling of particulate matter at HRS which will be used in the activities described under Task 2.2 of the project.

2 Selection of the sampling strategies

For the upcoming activities of MetHyTrucks, two commercial devices have been identified for adaptation to HD HRS particulate matter sampling: the HYDAC “PSA-H70” and the Airborne labs “MRM 7650”. They are planned to be used for sampling at HD-HRS. Additionally, one filter holder developed by Boyd and NEL for HD sampling is presented, but this is not yet part of a complete sampling system. This report is based on a recent review of sampling strategies for particulate matter in hydrogen fuel (at that time the article was written, the systems were exclusively adapted for LD-HDS) [5].

2.1 HYDAC PSA-H70 and PSA-H70 MC2

2.1.1 Description

The PSA-H70 is a high-pressure filter holder designed to be placed in series between an HRS nozzle and the receptacle of an FCEV or a simulated tank system used as sink. The system is constructed for 70 MPa and follow a regular fuelling protocol, so that no manual override of the HRS is required. To protect the filter from the initial test pulse of 87.5 MPa a rotary valve is installed upstream the filter to limit the pressure exerted on the filter. After the test pulse, the valve is put in a fully open position allowing for the full flow and pressure over the filter required for representative sampling.

The system is depressurized with a bleed valve before disconnection from HRS and FCEV is done. The adapter is shown in Figure 1.

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1 protective cap | 6 bleed valve |
| 2 receptacle | 7 fixing plate for containment grip (×2) |
| 3 rotary valve | 8 vent nozzle |
| 4 housing screws (×8) | 9 high pressure hydrogen hose |
| 5 grounding point for potential equalisation | |

Figure 1. HYDAC PSA-H70 sampling adapter.

In a MCP 02 version of the PSA-H70 released in 2018, the design was changed to remove the rotary and bleed valves. The rotary valve removal implies that filter substrate support needs to be replaced more frequently. The bleed valve was replaced by a feedback loop with check valves, allowing depressurization through the nozzle. The concept is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. HYDAC PSA-H70 MCP 02 version.

2.1.2 Adaptation for heavy-duty applications

The consortium is currently in dialog with HYDAC regarding adaptation of their system for HD conditions. The system was designed for 120 g/s flow so technically changing to high-flow (HF) nozzle and receptacle should be feasible. Since the system was designed for 70 Mpa application, there is a concern on how the MCP 02 version of the system with depressurization through the nozzle will work for 35 MPa applications as the nozzle will not allow depressurization.

With respect to safety, the removal of bleed valve is considered beneficial. There is no pressure relief valve installed on the system.

2.2 Airborne lab MRM-7650

2.2.1 Description

Airborne Labs have marketed a commercial implementation of ASTM D7650 [6] type sampling of particulate matter. Here, sampling from HRS is performed with HRS in manual dispensing mode. A two-way ball valve is installed upstream the filter. Venting is typically done with a vent stack, or with a simulated tank. A pressure relief valve is installed in the system.

The system is rated at 137 MPa and designed for a flow of 125 g/s. A schematic is given in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Schematic of MRM-7650.

2.2.2 Adaptation to HD applications

The sampling system should be compatible to HD applications by changing the receptacle. Initial discussion with Airborne labs has confirmed this and their willingness to collaborate with the project. They have raised some concerns about the dimensions of their vent system with respect to increased flow and possible heat formation from the release. This will be further discussed with Airborne in upcoming meetings.

2.3 Hy-Strainer T1050 heavy-duty particulate sampler

2.3.1 Description

This particle sampler was designed for heavy duty applications, e.g. higher than 60 g/s flow by Boyd Hydrogen and NEL. It is rated for 96.5 MPa at -40 to 50 °C. The system is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. HyStrainer T1050 schematic and image.

2.3.2 Adaptation to HD applications

There is no need for adaptation for the filter holder itself. However, a complete system is still lacking. The project consortium has initiated discussions with Boyd Hydrogen and Swagelok on how to make a suitable design.

3 Conclusion

Two commercial adapters have been selected for possible modification for HD application as requested by the activity description 2.2.1: the Hydac system and the Airborne system. In addition, a possible design for a dedicated HD sampling system using the filter holder described in section 2.3 will be proposed.

4 Bibliography

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